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Comparative Analysis Of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons In Four Selected Carbonated Drinks In Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the extent of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) concentration in some carbonated soft drinks commonly consumed in Nigeria. Coca cola, Fanta (Orange), Pepsi and La-Casera brands of carbonated soft drinks were analyzed using gas chromatography. Results obtained from the study revealed that pepsi contains the highest concentration of PAHs with a total mean concentration of 21.09ng/L among the soft drinks analyzed. Coca cola came next, containing 1901.49ng/L while fanta and la-casera contained 1276.067ng/L and 1014.31ng/L respectively. These figures are far above the World Health Organization recommended maximum permissible limit (200ng/L) for total PAHs in drinking water. These indicate that it may be unsafe to consume these soft drinks as their consumption may have negative health impacts

Keywords: Coca cola, Fanta (Orange), Pepsi, La-Casera, Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs)

INTRODUCTION

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) represent a class of organic compounds characterized by fused aromatic ring structures, which persist as pervasive environmental contaminants across atmospheric, aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems due to anthropogenic activities and natural processes. (Nakata *et al.*, 2014). PAHs constitute significant environmental contaminants, with numerous members of this chemical class demonstrating well-established toxicological hazards including acute toxicity, mutagenic potential, and carcinogenic activity in exposed organisms. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons primarily form through incomplete combustion of carbon-based fuels including coal, petroleum products and biomass, while natural origins include volcanic eruptions, forest fires and geological hydrocarbon seepage from coal and petroleum deposits. Primary human-derived sources of PAHs encompass residential heating systems, industrial operations including coal processing plants, petroleum refining activities, aluminum manufacturing facilities, and vehicular emissions, which collectively contribute substantial quantities of these pollutants to the environment. In ambient air, PAHs exist in both gaseous forms and as particulate-bound compounds adsorbed onto aerosol surfaces, with their phase distribution being strongly influenced by molecular weight and environmental conditions. They can be found in aquatic systems (Zhang *et al.*, 2012), soil (Yu *et al.*, 2019), air sample (Lammel *et al.*, 2010), food products (Yebra-Pimentel *et al.*, 2012) and urban street dust (Gope *et al.*, 2018).

Due to their lipophilic nature, PAHs are easily absorbed through the gastrointestinal tract in mammals and quickly distributed throughout various tissues, preferentially accumulating in adipose tissue.

It is estimated that the average global consumption of PAHs ranges from 0.02 to 3.6 µg/per day/ per person while in Nigeria, it ranges from 6.0 µg/ per day/per person (Diggs *et al.*, 2009). 2-12 % PAHs exposure is via inhalation while 88-98 % is via diet especially in the case of no smoking population (Essumang *et al.*, 2013). Soft drink may be liable to contamination by large deposits of PAHs incurred through various stages of production such as boiling and heating (Visciano *et al.*, 2006). They can also be incurred through air and soil into water used for industrial production of soft drinks (Orechio *et al.*, 2009). Other sources of PAHs in soft drinks include the use of plastic containers for canning and the level of industrial activities in the environment of production (Obini and Okafor, 2013). Highly industrialized or densely populated areas like Lagos, Aba, Enugu, Onitsha, and Port Harcourt in Nigeria are often associated with vast introduction of PAHs owing to the high level of anthropogenic activities such as increased heating and boiling, emissions from heavy power or gas plant, exhaust of generators, smoking, waste incineration and most importantly through emissions from motor vehicles, and other industrial processes (Nwachi *et al.*, 2016). Light PAHs (with fewer aromatic rings) tend to be more soluble, volatile and relatively mobile in the environment (Olatunji O.S., *et al.*, 2014), High molecular weight PAHs containing five or more aromatic rings exhibit greater environmental persistence and enhanced toxicity compared to their lighter counterparts. (Bolanos *et al.*, 2010).

Health Impacts of PAH Exposure in Humans

Dietary exposure to PAH-contaminated food significantly increases cancer risk, representing the most critical health concern associated with these compounds. (Huang and Penning 2014). Certain PAHs act as co-carcinogens, enhancing the cancer-causing effects of other carcinogens despite lacking significant carcinogenic activity themselves. Animal research demonstrates that PAH exposure primarily induces tumor formation in gastrointestinal tissues, particularly affecting the stomach and intestinal tract. (Huang and Penning 2014). Huang and Penning (2014) established that PAHs exert carcinogenic, mutagenic and teratogenic effects exclusively through formation of covalent PAH-DNA adducts, which disrupt normal genetic function.

Aside from being carcinogenic and mutagenic, beyond carcinogenic effects, PAHs demonstrate reproductive, developmental, immunotoxic, and neurotoxic potential. Their lipophilic nature enables transplacental transfer, exposing embryos and fetuses to these hazardous compounds during pregnancy. (Herbstman *et al.*, 2012). PAH-induced immunosuppression represents a significant immunotoxic effect, characterized by reduced immune competence that increases vulnerability to both infectious pathogens and malignant cell proliferation (Huang and Penning 2014).

Although PAH toxicity to major organ systems is well-documented, recent research has increasingly focused on their immunotoxic effects given the significant potential consequences for human disease susceptibility and immune function.

Effects on Immune Function: PAHs have been shown to modulate immune function through complex interactions with the immune system. Studies have demonstrated that exposure to PAHs can lead to alterations in immune cell populations, cytokine production, and immune responses, ultimately affecting host defense mechanisms against pathogens (Hahm *et al.*, 2019). For instance, PAH exposure has been associated with changes in the distribution and activity of immune cells, including macrophages, lymphocytes, and dendritic cells, which play crucial roles in innate and adaptive immunity (Hahm *et al.*, 2019). PAHs disrupt immune homeostasis by altering cytokine production profiles, differentially modulating pro-inflammatory (e.g., IL-1 β , TNF- α) and anti-inflammatory (e.g., IL-10) signaling pathways, thereby dysregulating normal inflammatory responses. (Burchiel *et al.*, 2019). These immunomodulatory effects of PAHs have significant implications for the body's ability to mount an effective immune response and maintain immune homeostasis.

Mechanisms of Immunotoxicity: The immunotoxic effects of PAHs are mediated through various mechanisms, reflecting their diverse chemical properties and biological interactions. PAH toxicity is largely mediated through activation of the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR), a ligand-dependent transcription factor that regulates expression of genes involved in xenobiotic metabolism and immune responses. (Hahm *et al.*, 2019). PAH binding induces AhR conformational changes, prompting nuclear translocation and subsequent regulation of genes controlling immune cell development, cytokine

signaling, and immunological functions. (Hahm *et al.*, 2019). PAH exposure triggers excessive reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, causing oxidative damage to immune cells and compromising their normal function through lipid peroxidation, protein oxidation and DNA damage. (Knaapen *et al.*, 2004). Furthermore, PAHs may directly interfere with immune cell function, impairing their ability to recognize and eliminate pathogens, thereby compromising host defense mechanisms (Hahm *et al.*, 2019).

Human Health Implications: The immunotoxicity of PAHs has significant implications for human health, particularly in populations with chronic or high-level exposure to these compounds. Occupational exposure to PAHs, such as in industries involving coal tar, asphalt, or combustion processes, may increase the risk of immune-related disorders, including infectious diseases, asthma, allergies, and autoimmune diseases (Burchiel *et al.*, 2019). General population exposure to environmental PAHs (vehicle exhaust, industrial emissions, tobacco smoke) presents comparable health risks, particularly for vulnerable subgroups including children, elderly individuals and immunocompromised persons. (Burchiel *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, the immunotoxic effects of PAHs may exacerbate existing health disparities, disproportionately affecting socioeconomically disadvantaged communities and populations with limited access to healthcare services.

Consumption of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons

PAHs in Food

Global average PAH intake ranges from 0.02-3.6 $\mu\text{g/day/person}$, while Nigerian populations experience significantly higher exposure levels averaging 6.0 $\mu\text{g/day/person}$, reflecting regional environmental contamination differences. (Diggs *et al.*, 2009). 2-12% PAHs exposure is via inhalation while 88-98 % is via diet especially in the case of non-smoking population (Essumang *et al.*, 2013). PAH contamination in food is widespread, resulting from both natural processes and environmental pollution, particularly through atmospheric particulate deposition onto crops and soil (Smith *et al.*, 2001).

Research indicates that 79-99% of human PAH exposure occurs through dietary intake, with estimated total consumption reaching approximately 2.5 μg per day from food sources. (Menzie *et al.*, 1992). Various cooking methods including grilling, smoking, frying, and baking can generate PAHs through thermal decomposition of organic materials and lipid pyrolysis. (Perelló *et al.*, 2009). PAH contamination has been detected in foods preserved through traditional methods like drying and curing, demonstrating these processes can introduce or concentrate these carcinogens. (de Vos *et al.* 1990). PAH contamination ($\mu\text{g/kg}$ levels) has been documented across diverse food categories including roasted coffee (Guatemala-Morales *et al.*, 2016), dairy products (Sun *et al.*, 2020), smoked meats (Zachara *et al.*, 2017) and plant-based foods (Jia *et al.*, 2018), demonstrating widespread dietary exposure potential.

PAHs in Beverages

Research has consistently detected concerning levels of PAHs in common beverages including tea, coffee, dairy products, alcoholic drinks, and soft drinks. Extensive analytical studies have investigated both the concentrations and sources of these contaminants across different drink Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are pervasive environmental contaminants detected across multiple matrices including atmospheric, terrestrial, aquatic, and food systems - with significant concentrations frequently found in beverage products. (Boušová *et al.*, 2020). This section explores the sources of PAH contamination in beverages, the potential health implications of PAH exposure through consumption, and strategies to mitigate PAH levels in beverages.

The presence of PAHs in beverages presents serious public health concerns due to their carcinogenic, mutagenic, and endocrine-disrupting effects. Effective risk reduction requires collaborative strategies involving improved production methods, stricter regulatory standards, enhanced packaging technologies, and comprehensive quality monitoring throughout the supply chain. By adopting these strategies, the beverage industry can minimize PAH exposure and safeguard consumer health.

PAHs in Soft Drinks

Soft drink may be liable to contamination by large deposits of PAHs incurred through various stages of production such as boiling and heating (Visciano *et al.*, 2006). They can also be incurred through air and soil into water used for industrial production of soft drinks (Orechio *et al.*, 2009). Other sources of PAHs in soft drinks include the use of plastic containers for canning and the level of industrial activities in the

environment of production (Obini and Okafor, 2013). Highly industrialized or densely populated areas like Lagos, Aba, Enugu, Onitsha, and Port Harcourt in Nigeria are often associated with vast introduction of PAHs owing to the high level of anthropogenic activities such as increased heating and boiling, emissions from heavy power or gas plant, exhaust of generators, smoking, waste incineration and most importantly through emissions from motor vehicles, and other industrial processes (Nwachi *et al.*, 2016). Light PAHs (with fewer aromatic rings) tend to be more soluble, volatile and relatively mobile in the environment (Olatunji *et al.*, 2014), High-molecular-weight PAHs, characterized by five or more fused aromatic rings, exhibit greater environmental persistence and enhanced toxicity compared to their lighter counterparts due to their chemical stability and bioaccumulation potential. (Bolanos *et al.*, 2010).

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) have been detected as contaminants in multiple food and beverage categories, including carbonated soft drinks, posing potential health risks to consumers. This section explores the sources of PAH contamination in soft drinks, the potential health concerns associated with PAH exposure, and strategies to mitigate PAH levels in these beverages.

PAH contamination in soft drinks presents significant health risks to consumers due to their carcinogenic, mutagenic, endocrine-disrupting, and immunotoxic properties. Mitigating PAH levels in soft drinks requires collaborative efforts from producers, regulators, and consumers to address contamination sources, optimize production processes, implement packaging solutions, ensure quality control, and educate consumers. By adopting these strategies, the soft drink industry can minimize PAH exposure and safeguard consumer health.

Soft Drinks

Soft drinks are non-alcoholic beverages typically containing sweeteners (natural/artificial), food acids, and flavorings (plant-derived or synthetic), available in carbonated or non-carbonated forms. Historically marketed as alternatives to alcoholic beverages, they emerged as temperance movement substitutes in 19th century America. According to Euromonitor International, a global market intelligence publisher, Nigeria ranks as the world's fourth-largest soft drink consumer, with annual sales reaching approximately 38.6 million liters. A concerning study revealed 97% of surveyed adolescents (n=1,000) consumed at least 35cl daily, highlighting significant overconsumption patterns.

Carbonated Drinks

Carbonated beverages are artificially infused with carbon dioxide gas, typically containing high concentrations of added sugars (40-50g per serving), empty calories (150-200 kcal), and often caffeine, while offering minimal nutritional benefit. Damle *et al.*, (2011) identified the key components of carbonated beverages as phosphoric acid (pH <3, comparable to acetic acid), sucrose/high-fructose corn syrup, caffeine and synthetic color/flavor additives, which collectively define their sensory and chemical properties. The Nigerian carbonated beverage market is dominated by international brands (Coca-Cola, Pepsi, Sprite, 7Up) and local products (Lacaser, Biggie Cola), along with malt-based drinks and flavored sodas, reflecting diverse consumer preferences.

Coca-Cola

Coca-Cola is a carbonated beverage produced by The Coca-Cola Company, originally developed in 1886 by pharmacist John Stith Pemberton in Atlanta, Georgia as a medicinal temperance alternative to alcoholic drinks. (Eschner, 2017). The beverage's name derives from its historic ingredients: coca leaf extract and kola nuts (providing caffeine), though its modern formulation remains a proprietary secret protected by the Coca-Cola Company.

The Coca-Cola Company manufactures a proprietary syrup concentrate that is distributed to authorized bottling partners worldwide. These licensed bottlers, operating under exclusive territorial agreements, produce the final beverage by mixing the concentrate with purified water and sweeteners before packaging in cans or bottles. Coca-Cola dominates global carbonated beverage consumption, with its corporate data indicating distribution across 200+ countries and daily consumption exceeding 1.9 billion servings worldwide, making it Nigeria's and the world's most popular soft drink.

The Coca-Cola Company has expanded its product line beyond the original formula, introducing multiple variants including Diet Coke (the most successful), caffeine-free options, zero-sugar versions,

and flavor-infused editions like cherry, vanilla, and coffee. From 1985-2009, the flagship product was rebranded as Coca-Cola Classic to differentiate it from the reformulated "New Coke."

Coca cola (www.businessinsider.com)

Pepsi

Pepsi, a carbonated soft drink produced by PepsiCo, originated in 1893 as "Brad's Drink" created by pharmacist Caleb Bradham in New Bern, North Carolina. Renamed Pepsi-Cola in 1898, the brand was simplified to Pepsi in 1961, maintaining its original formulation as a digestive aid and energy booster.

Pepsi (Nairametrics.com)

La Casera

La Casera ranks among Nigeria's top-selling carbonated beverages, distinguished by its apple juice base that differentiates it from conventional colas, offering a fruit-flavored alternative in the soft drink market. It is traditionally a Spanish drink but has grown to be a household drink in Nigeria. It is the first-ever soft drink to be offered in a plastic bottle in Nigeria (thelacaseracompany.com).

La Casera (drinkallotters.com.ng)

Fanta

Fanta is another carbonated soft drink that is widely consumed globally and particularly in Nigeria. Fanta, originally developed in 1940s Nazi Germany by Coca-Cola Deutschland's Max Keith during Coca-Cola ingredient shortages, became a successful fruit-flavored alternative with 3 million 1943 sales. The modern formulation emerged from 1955 Italian development, now offering 200+ global flavors under Coca-Cola ownership. The orange flavoured brand is the most commonly consumed Fanta in Nigeria.

Fanta (drinkalotters.com.ng)

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Collection of Samples

Samples were bought from super markets in Yenagoa town, Bayelsa State, Nigeria and was kept in a temperature of 4°C until analysis.

Extraction PAHs

PAH extraction followed modified ASTM 3415 protocol: samples (27mL borosilicate MacCartney bottles) underwent 2-hour sonication with 10mL 3:1 hexane:DCM solvent, followed by organic phase filtration into 250mL borosilicate beakers for hydrocarbon isolation.

3.3 PAH Separation

Hydrocarbon fractionation was performed using column chromatography with a 10.0 g activated neutral alumina (grade 1) stationary phase packed in a glass column. The aliphatic fraction was first eluted using redistilled hexane and collected in a pre-cleaned 20.0 mL glass container. Subsequently, the PAH-containing fraction was recovered through sequential elution with a 3:1 (v/v) hexane:dichloromethane mixture followed by pure redistilled dichloromethane, with the final PAH fraction collected into a pre-cleaned borosilicate beaker.

The extract was concentrated to 1.0 mL using nitrogen evaporation before chromatography analysis.

Gas Chromatography (GC) Analysis

The concentrated extract (1.0 mL, nitrogen-evaporated) was analyzed via whole oil GC using 1-2 µL injections through the heated inlet port into the chromatographic column for hydrocarbon separation and detection..

The gas chromatography conditions were as follows

GC	HP6890 with HP Chemem Station Rev.A09.01 [1206] software.
Injection temperature	Split injection
Slit ratio	20:1
Carrier gas	Nitrogen
Inlet temperature	250°C
Column type	HP-1
Column dimension	30mx0.25mx0.25µm
Oven programme	Initial temperature @60°C for 5 minutes First ramping @15°C/min for 14 minutes, maintained for 3 minutes Second ramping @10°C/min for 5 minutes, maintained for 4 minutes.

RESULTS

PAH concentrations in Coca-Cola, Fanta, and LaCasera samples from both study and control areas are presented in Tables 4.1-4.4. Results, quantified at the instrument detection limit (1×10^{-3} mg/kg), represent individual PAH peaks identified on GC-FID chromatograms in $\mu\text{g/L}$ units.

Results obtained (Table 4.1) showed that total concentration of PAHs in Coca Cola is 1901.49 ng/L. Fluorene has the highest concentration among all PAHs with a mean value of 949.49 ng/L. Acenaphthene follows with a mean concentration of 184.03ng/L while Fluoranthene also shows a high level at 213.18ng/L. Results also showed some moderate PAH Levels. Pyrene (156.35ng/L) and Anthracene (86.13ng/L) are at moderate levels. Phenanthrene (56.27ng/L) and Naphthalene (48.38ng/L) also fall into the moderate range. Benzo(g,h,i)perylene has a mean level of 47.77ng/L. Acenaphthylene is present at 47.71ng/L. The PAHs with low levels include Chrysene (18.23ng/L), Dibenz(a,h)anthracene (20.84ng/L), Benzo(b)fluoranthene (8.64ng/L), Benzo(k)fluoranthene (9.21ng/L), Benzo(a)pyrene (9.18ng/L), and Benzo(a) anthracene (6.547ng/L). Indeno(1,2,3-cd) pyrene has the lowest concentration at 5.45ng/L.

Table 4.1: Overall Values for Levels of PAHs in (ng/L) in Coca Cola

PAH	Sample 1 (ng/L)	Sample 2 (ng/L)	Sample 3 (ng/L)	Mean (ng/L)
Naphthalene	47.71	49.56	47.88	48.38+1.02
Acenaphthylene	48.69	47.74	46.88	47.71+1.07
Acenaphthene	184.09	182.66	185.33	184.03+0.91
Fluorene	949.71	947.33	951.44	949.49+1.34
Phenanthrene	55.9	57.08	55.82	56.27+2.1
Anthracene	85.69	83.76	88.95	86.13+0.71
Fluoranthene	212.19	210.45	216.89	213.18+2.62
Pyrene	156.67	158.95	153.44	156.35+3.33
Benzo(a)anthracene	6.51	7.11	6.02	6.547+2.77
Chrysene	18.5	16.34	19.86	18.23+0.54
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	10.67	10.44	9.85	8.64+0.42
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	8.91	7.66	9.34	9.21+0.87
Benzo(a)pyrene	9.28	9.18	9.09	9.18.32+1.77
Indeno(1,2,3, c d)pyrene	5.48	5.62''	5.24	5.45+0.1782.55+ 0.19
Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene	82.77	80.11	84.78	20.84+ 2.34
Benzo(g,h,i)Perylene	24.09	24.89	13.54	47.77+ 6.33
TOTAL PAH				1901.49

Results obtained from (Table 4.2) showed that the total concentration of PAHs in Fanta is 1276.067ng/L. Results also showed that Fluoranthene has the highest concentration at $237.59 \pm 11.38 \text{ ng/L}$., Acenaphthene follows with a concentration of $215.4 \pm 0.64 \text{ ng/L}$ and then Pyrene at $185.05 \pm 5.05 \text{ ng/L}$. PAHs with moderate levels include Naphthalene, present at $85.24 \pm 11.90 \text{ ng/L}$, Acenaphthylene has a concentration of $63.48 \pm 5.05 \text{ ng/L}$, Phenanthrene and Anthracene are at $66.28 \pm 1.07 \text{ ng/L}$ and $104.80 \pm 1.78 \text{ ng/L}$, respectively and Fluorene is present at $111.25 \pm 1.55 \text{ ng/L}$. Low Levels PAHs include Benzo(a)anthracene: $14.41 \pm 1.94 \text{ ng/L}$, Chrysene: $22.47 \pm 1.54 \text{ ng/L}$, Benzo(b)fluoranthene: $12.10 \pm 1.56 \text{ ng/L}$, Benzo(k)fluoranthene: $14.19 \pm 2.23 \text{ ng/L}$, Benzo(a)pyrene: $11.01 \pm 1.07 \text{ ng/L}$, Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene: $5.97 \pm 0.67 \text{ ng/L}$, Dibenz(a,h) anthracene: $100.41 \pm 10.89 \text{ ng/L}$ and Benzo(g,h,i)perylene: $26.43 \pm 1.78 \text{ ng/L}$.

Table 4.2: Overall Values for Levels of PAHs in (ng/L) in Fanta

PAH	Sample 1 (ng/L)	Sample 2 (ng/L)	Sample 3 (ng/L)	Mean ((ng/L))
Naphthalene	86.40	83.88	85.44	85.24±11.90
Acenaphthylene	60.45	66.62	63.37	63.48±5.05
Acenaphthene	211.78	218.86	215.56	215.4±0.64
Fluorene	114.62	107.66	111.46	111.25±1.55
Phenanthrene	64.08	68.54	66.21	66.28±1.07
Anthracene	109.56	100.78	104.06	104.80±1.78
Fluoranthene	225.76	249.56	237.45	237.59±11.38
Pyrene	190.45	180.44	184.27	185.05±5.05
Benzo(a)anthracene	13.78	15.06	14.38	14.41±1.94
Chrysene	24.11	21.03	22.28	22.47±1.54
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	11.02	13.16	12.12	12.10±1.56
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	15.89	12.34	14.35	14.19±2.23
Benzo(a)pyrene	12.08	9.45	11.49	11.01±1.07
Indeno(1,2,3,cd)pyrene	5.86	6.04	6.00	5.97±0.67
Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene	102.04	98.74	100.44	100.41±10.89
Benzo(g,h,i)Perylene	28.54	24.72	26.02	26.43±1.78
Total PAH				1276.067

Results obtained from (Table 4.3) showed that the total concentration of PAHs in La Casera is 1014.31ng/L. Fluoranthene has the highest concentration at 315.70±8.78ng/L. Acenaphthene follows with a concentration of 161.07±5.28ng/L. Anthracene comes next at 137.53±5.90ng/L and then Pyrene with a concentration of 107.91±10.87ng/L. Those with moderate levels include Acenaphthylene: 42.7±4.37ng/L, Fluorene: 61.39±6.30 ng/L, Phenanthrene: 52.35±6.07ng/L, Dibenzo(a,h) anthracene: 51.73±6.74ng/L, Chrysene: 14.50±1.11ng/L, Benzo(b)fluoranthene: 14.67±2.02 ng/. Benzo(k) fluoranthene: 12.30±1.24ng/L, Benzo(a)anthracene: 10.89±2.34ng/L, Benzo(g,h,i) perylene: 10.52 ± 1.45 ng/L and Benzo(a) pyrene: 10.10±1.98 ng/L. Naphthalene and Indeno(1,2,3-cd) pyrene were the lowest at 6.47±2.16ng/L and: 4.47±0.69ng/L respectively.

Table 4.3: Overall values for levels of PAHs in (ng/L) in LaCasera

PAH	Sample 1 (ng/L)	Sample 2 (ng/L)	Sample 3 (ng/L)	Mean (ng/L)
Naphthalene	4.34	8.66	6.41	6.47±2.16
Acenaphthylene	37.85	46.32	43.98	42.7±4.37
Acenaphthene	155.88	166.44	160.89	161.07±5.28
Fluorene	54.88	67.44	61.84	61.39±6.30
Phenanthrene	46.30	58.44	52.32	52.35±6.07
Anthracene	131.62	143.42	137.56	137.53±5.90
Fluoranthene	305.85	318.51	322.73	315.70±8.78
Pyrene	116.54	95.71	111.49	107.91±10.87
Benzo(a)anthracene	8.45	13.11	11.10	10.89±2.34
Chrysene	15.44	13.28	14.77	14.50±1.11
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	16.92	13.01	14.08	14.67±2.02
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	10.98	13.43	12.48	12.30±1.24
Benzo(a)pyrene	12.06	8.11	10.13	10.10±1.98
Indeno(1,2,3,cd)pyrene	5.22	3.86	4.34	4.47±0.69
Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene	44.86	58.34	51.99	51.73±6.74
Benzo(g,h,i)Perylene	8.98	11.86	10.71	10.52±1.45
Total PAH				1014.31

Results of analysis of Pepsi sample shows that fluorene is the highest at 957.00 ng/L and Benzo(k)fluoranthene being the lowest at 4.66ng/L. Results obtained (Table 4.4) showed that the total concentration of PAHs in Pepsi is 2109.51ng/L. Fluorene has the highest concentration at 957.00±6.59ng/L, followed by Fluoranthene at 282.40±9.44ng/L. Pyrene follows with a concentration of 225.69±7.14ng/L while Acenaphthenecomes next with 198.60±3.69ng/L. Naphthalene: 7.56±0.64ng/L, Acenaphthylene: 62.92±3.52ng/L, Phenanthrene: 77.57±11.79ng/L, Anthracene: 123.99±5.34ng/L Benzo(a) anthracene: 17.42±2.62ng/L, Chrysene: 12.44±0.79ng/L, Benzo(b) fluoranthene: 11.03±1.74ng/L, Benzo(k) fluoranthene: 4.66±0.85ng/L, Benzo(a)pyrene: 1.38±0.38ng/L, Indeno(1,2,3-cd) pyrene: 6.33±1.00ng/L, Dibenzo(a,h) anthracene: 97.08±2.97ng/L and Benzo(g,h,i) perylene: 23.43±2.40ng/L respectively showed moderate levels. The PAHs with the lowest levels are Naphthalene: 7.56±0.64 ng/L, Benzo(a)pyrene: 1.38±0.38ng/L, Indeno(1,2,3-cd) pyrene: 6.33±1.00ng/L and Benzo(k) fluoranthene: 4.66 ± 0.85ng/L.

Quantification of the individual PAHs in the four soft drinks analysed revealed that Naphthalene levels were highest in Fanta at 85.24ng/L and lowest in La Casera at 6.47ng/L. Similarly, acenaphthylene was most concentrated in Fanta, reaching 63.48 ng/L, and least concentrated in La Casera at 42.7ng/L. Acenaphthene also followed this pattern, with the highest level in Fanta at 215.4ng/L and the lowest in La Casera at 161.07ng/L. In terms of fluorene, Pepsi had the highest level at 957.00ng/L, while La Casera had the lowest at 61.39 ng/L. Phenanthrene was most abundant in Pepsi (77.57ng/L) and least in La Casera (52.35 ng/L). Anthracene levels were highest in La Casera at 137.53ng/L and lowest in Coca Cola at 86.13 ng/L. Fluoranthene was found in the highest concentration in La Casera (315.70ng/L) and in the lowest in Fanta (237.59ng/L). Pyrene levels were greatest in Pepsi at 225.69ng/L and smallest in La Casera at 107.91ng/L. Benzo(a)anthracene had its highest concentration in Pepsi (17.42ng/L) and its lowest in Coca Cola (6.547ng/L). Chrysene levels peaked in Fanta at 22.47ng/L and were lowest in La Casera at 14.50ng/L.

Benzo(b)fluoranthene was highest in La Casera (14.67ng/L) and lowest in Coca Cola (8.64ng/L). Benzo(k)fluoranthene levels were most significant in Fanta (14.19ng/L) and least in Pepsi (4.66ng/L). Benzo(a)pyrene was most concentrated in Fanta at 11.01ng/L and least in Pepsi at 1.38 ng/L. Indeno(1,2,3-cd) pyrene was highest in Fanta (5.97ng/L) and lowest in La Casera (4.47ng/L). Dibenzo(a,h) anthracene levels were highest in Fanta at 100.41 ng/L and lowest in Coca Cola at 20.84ng/L. Lastly, benzo(g,h,i)perylene was most abundant in Coca Cola (47.77ng/L) and least in La Casera (10.52ng/L).

The analysis indicates that Pepsi has the highest total PAH levels, followed by Coca Cola, with Fanta and La Casera having lower levels. Specific PAH compounds vary in concentration across the four beverages, with some being significantly higher in one drink compared to the others. The presence of PAHs in these popular beverages underscores the importance of monitoring and regulating such contaminants to ensure consumer safety. Further studies could explore the sources of these PAHs and strategies for reducing their presence in carbonated drinks.

Table 4.4: Overall Values for Levels of PAHs in (ng/L) in Pepsi

PAH	Sample 1 (ng/L)	Sample 2 (ng/L)	Sample 3 (ng/L)	Mean (ng/L)
Naphthalene	6.87	8.13	7.69	7.56±0.64
Acenaphthylene	59.68	66.66	62.43	62.92±3.52
Acenaphthene	195.08	202.44	198.29	198.60±3.69
Fluorene	963.73	950.56	956.71	957.00±6.59
Phenanthrene	89.45	65.87	77.38	77.57±11.79
Anthracene	118.66	129.34	123.97	123.99±5.34
Fluoranthene	273	291.88	282.33	282.40±9.44
Pyrene	232.82	218.54	225.72	225.69±7.14
Benzo(a)anthracene	14.88	20.11	17.27	17.42±2.62
Chrysene	11.87	13.34	12.11	12.44±0.79
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	10.11	13.04	9.94	11.03±1.74
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	3.87	5.56	4.54	4.66±0.85
Benzo(a)pyrene	1.80	1.05	1.30	1.38±0.38
Indeno(1,2,3,cd)pyrene	7.34	5.34	6.31	6.33±1.00
Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene	100.06	94.12	97.06	97.08±2.97
Benzo(g,h,i)Perylene	25.86	21.06	23.36	23.43±2.40
Total PAH				2109.51

DISCUSSION

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) represent a class of persistent organic pollutants characterized by fused aromatic ring structures, which are ubiquitously distributed across atmospheric, aquatic, and terrestrial environmental compartments. (Nakata *et al.*, 2014). PAHs and their reactive metabolites pose significant health risks by forming covalent adducts with DNA and cellular proteins, causing mutagenesis, teratogenesis, and carcinogenesis. Epidemiological studies of occupationally exposed workers demonstrate elevated risks for skin, lung, bladder, and gastrointestinal cancers following chronic PAH mixture exposure. (IARC, 1987). PAHs demonstrate comprehensive immunotoxic effects, including suppression of hematopoietic progenitor cells (pre-B, pre-T, myeloid lineages), inhibition of lymphocyte proliferation, induction of lymphoid apoptosis, disruption of granulocyte-monocyte differentiation, and dysregulation of macrophage cytokine signaling networks. (Rengarajan *et al.*, 2015). PAH exposure can promote oncogenesis through immunosuppression while simultaneously inducing pathological immune activation, potentially triggering hypersensitivity reactions and autoimmune responses through molecular mimicry and epitope spreading mechanisms. (Abdel-Shafy and Mansour, 2016). PAHs exert immunotoxic effects by binding to aryl hydrocarbon receptors (AhRs) in immune cells, inducing cytochrome P450 enzymes (CYP1A1, CYP1B1) that generate reactive oxygen species and electrophilic intermediates, ultimately disrupting normal immune function through oxidative stress and macromolecular damage (Marris *et al.*, 2020).

The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) has classified PAHs into four carcinogenicity categories: Group 1 (confirmed human carcinogens), Group 2A (probable human carcinogens), Group 2B (possible human carcinogens), and Group 3 (unclassifiable as to human carcinogenicity), based on epidemiological and experimental evidence. (Ghosal *et al.*, 2016). Only benzo[a]pyrene is classified by IARC as a proven human carcinogen (Group 1) among PAHs. (IARC, 2010). Benzo[a]pyrene's Group 1 classification stems from well-characterized metabolic activation to benzo[a]pyrene diol epoxide (BPDE), which forms mutagenic DNA adducts (e.g., anti-BPDE-dG) in exposed workers, as documented in IARC (2010) monographs. These lesions induce characteristic mutations in both human and rodent cells.

Benzo(a)pyrene, recognized as the initial identified chemical carcinogen, ranks among the most carcinogenic polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and is commonly employed as a biomarker for exposure in risk evaluations (Lee and Vu, 2010). According to Smith *et al.* (2007), this compound has been shown to cause infertility in males by adversely affecting the reproductive system. Research has

demonstrated that naphthalene, benzo(a)anthracene, and benzo(a)pyrene induce toxic effects on embryos in animal studies (Rengarajan *et al.*, 2015; Abdel-Shafy and Mansour, 2016). These chemicals potentially exhibit antiestrogenic and antiandrogenic activity through direct interaction with estrogen and androgen receptor sites (Bolden *et al.* 2017). Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) exposure induces both morphological and physiological alterations in bone marrow tissue. Given its primary role in hematopoiesis and immune cell generation, these changes can have significant systemic health implications (Hrudkova *et al.*, 2004). A Immunotoxic effects from PAH exposure require substantially higher concentrations compared to carcinogenic effects (Burchiel and Gao, 2014).

This study was carried out to determine the presence and levels of polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in four different brands of carbonated soft drinks- Coca cola, Fanta (orange), Pepsi and LaCasera popularly consumed in Nigeria. All 16 polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons designated as priority pollutants by the US EPA were identified in the soft drinks, though their concentrations varied significantly. (Tables 4.1, 4.2,4.3 and 4.4). Results obtained from the study revealed that Pepsi contains the highest concentration of PAHs with a total mean concentration of 21.09 ng/L among the soft drinks analysed. Coca cola comes next, containing 1901.49ng/L while Fanta and La casera contain about 1276.06 ng/L and 1014.31ng/L respectively. These figures are far above the World Health Organization recommended maximum permissible limit (200ng/L) for total PAHs in drinking water (WHO, 2003). This contamination by PAHs could be due to atmospheric input of PAHs in the water used for the production. Another source of PAHs in the soft drinks could be from the water or containers used in the production of soft drink production. This indicates that it may be unsafe to consume these soft drinks as their consumption may have negative health implications.

CONCLUSION

Results obtained showed that soft drink in Nigeria may be contaminated with high levels of PAHs. This call for great concern as it is inimical to the health of the people and the environment.

RECOMMENDATION

More studies is needed to identify the source of elevated PAH concentrations in Nigerian soft drinks.

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